
BiLSTM-CNN With Attention For Remaining Useful Life Prediction In Turbofan Engines

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Abstract

Predictive maintenance is critical for ensuring the reliability and efficiency of complex machinery, especially in industrial environments. In this work, a hybrid deep learning model is developed that combines recurrent and convolutional architectures with attention mechanisms to predict the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of aircraft engines using the CMAPSS dataset. By integrating temporal modeling with spatial feature extraction and adaptive attention, the proposed approach effectively captures both long-term dependencies and local degradation patterns. The model was evaluated in all subsets and demonstrated competitive performance in terms of prediction accuracy and generalization. This study highlights the potential of hybrid architectures for real-world prognostic applications.

1 Introduction

Modern industrial systems, such as aircraft engines, wind turbines, and manufacturing equipment, rely on continuous monitoring to ensure operational safety, reduce downtime, and optimize maintenance schedules. Predictive maintenance, the task of forecasting the remaining Useful Life (RUL) of machinery [19], plays a central role in this paradigm. Accurate prediction of RUL allows operators to intervene proactively before failure occurs, thus avoiding costly repairs or catastrophic breakdowns.

Traditional approaches [2] to RUL prediction have relied heavily on physics-based models or hand-crafted features. Although effective in some contexts, these methods often struggle to adapt to complex and nonlinear degradation processes present in real-world systems. In recent years, data-driven methods, particularly deep learning, have shown significant promise in learning representations directly from multivariate sensor time series without extensive domain-specific feature engineering.

This paper presents a hybrid deep learning model for RUL prediction that combines bidirectional recurrent networks, dilated convolutional layers, and attention mechanisms. Our architecture is designed to leverage the strengths of temporal modeling, hierarchical feature extraction, and dynamic focus on salient input patterns. The interpretability and performance of the model is enhanced by incorporating Convolutional Block Attention Modules (CBAM) and positional encoding to improve temporal and spatial awareness.

The model was evaluated on the well-established CMAPSS dataset [17]. Our results demonstrate that this hybrid approach achieves competitive predictive accuracy while maintaining generalization, even in the presence of sensor noise and operating condition variability.

2 Related Works

Accurate Remaining Useful Life (RUL) prediction has received considerable attention in the Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) domain [33], with diverse deep learning approaches [30] developed to model temporal and sensor dynamics effectively. To gather more data for Engine Health Monitoring (EHM), some studies have combined fuzzy logic [8, 35], while others have used support vectors [9] or gradient boosting trees [21]. While model-based approaches-such as those proposed in [1, 7] have shown promise, they typically rely on detailed prior knowledge of the underlying physical systems, which is often unavailable or difficult to obtain in real-world scenarios. Machine learning models have significantly influenced the field due to their ability to capture highly nonlinear, complex, and multi-dimensional relationships without requiring extensive prior prognostic knowledge. In the context of RUL estimation, early efforts explored the use of multi-layer perceptrons (MLPs), as demonstrated in [23], where the authors reported improved prediction performance over traditional model-based techniques.

Wang et al. [26] introduce FC-STGNN, a graph neural network framework that captures spatial-temporal dependencies in multivariate time-series data using fully connected graphs and pooling operations. Their model shows promise in predictive maintenance tasks, including C-MAPSS, by modeling sensor relationships across both space and time.

Costa and Sánchez [4] propose a variational encoding approach that uses recurrent encoder-regressor models with latent space representations for interpretable RUL estimation. Their method emphasizes both prediction accuracy and interpretability through a variational inference loss.

Several works have explored convolutional techniques for efficiency and scalability. Pantiskas et al. [15] propose LightWaveS, a time-series classification framework combining wavelet scattering and random kernels to reduce feature redundancy and improve efficiency, particularly in edge computing environments.

In the context of anomaly detection, Sipple [22] presents an unsupervised approach that uses negative sampling to simulate failures and integrated gradients for attributing anomalies to input features, enabling high interpretability in IoT settings.

Li et al. [10] introduce a multi-scale deep CNN (MS-DCNN) architecture that performs RUL prediction by extracting multi-resolution features using parallel convolutional blocks. Their results on the C-MAPSS dataset demonstrate superior performance without increasing computational burden.

Unsupervised learning has also been explored for robust RUL prediction. Ellefsen et al. [5] propose a semi-supervised architecture that incorporates unsupervised pre-training with supervised learning. Their use of a genetic algorithm to tune hyperparameters enhances performance even with limited labeled data.

Earlier works using traditional sequence models such as HMMs and RNNs have shown limitations in capturing long-term dependencies. Zheng et al. [34] address this by introducing an LSTM-based model, which can better exploit sensor sequences and model temporal patterns. Their model significantly outperforms both regression-based and CNN-based baselines on PHM datasets.

Together, these studies highlight the shift from classical models to hybrid, interpretable, and scalable architectures that better capture the complexity of degradation patterns in real-world machinery.

3 Methodology

This section describes the architecture of the proposed hybrid model for predicting the remaining useful life (RUL). Our approach combines bidirectional recurrent layers[34, 32, 18] with dilated convolutional blocks[16, 11, 12] and attention mechanisms [24], enabling the model to capture both temporal dependencies and spatial patterns present in multivariate sensor data.

3.1 Input Representation and Positional Encoding

Each input sequence consists of time-series sensor readings from a single engine unit. Before modeling, a custom Positional Encoding Layer [3] inspired by transformer architectures is applied to

inject explicit temporal information into the sequence. This helps preserve the relative order of time steps, especially important in non-recurrent components such as convolutions and attention layers.

3.2 Bidirectional LSTM Layers

To model sequential dependencies in both forward and backward directions, a stack of two Bidirectional LSTM layers [20] is employed, with 96 and 48 hidden units respectively. These layers are designed to capture long-term trends and contextual degradation behavior from sensor sequences, forming a strong temporal baseline.

3.3 Transformer-Based Attention Block

Following the BiLSTM stack, a Transformer block based on multi-head self-attention [25] is introduced. This allows the model to dynamically weigh the importance of different time steps across the sequence, capturing interactions that may not be local in time. The attention output is normalized and passed through a feed-forward network with dropout for regularization.

3.4 Residual Dilated Convolutional Blocks

To further extract hierarchical temporal features, two residual dilated convolutional blocks [31] are stacked, with kernel size 5 and dilation rates of 1 and 2, respectively. These blocks capture fine-to-coarse patterns in the time series, while residual connections preserve feature flow and mitigate vanishing gradients.

Each block includes two convolutional layers followed by Layer Normalization, ReLU activation, and Dropout. If the input and output dimensions mismatch, a 1×1 convolution is applied to the shortcut path to match dimensions.

3.5 Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM)

To refine learned representations, a CBAM module [27] is appended, which enhances the model's focus on important sensor channels and time steps. CBAM consists of two submodules:

- Channel attention: Learns to emphasize informative sensors based on global pooling across time.
- Spatial attention: Identifies key time steps by aggregating across channels and applying a convolutional attention map.

This dual attention structure improves robustness to noise and variation across units.

3.6 Prediction Head

The final representation is passed through a Global Average Pooling layer, followed by a fully connected layer with ReLU activation and dropout. The final output is a single scalar representing the predicted Remaining Useful Life.

3.7 Loss Function and Optimization

The Huber loss is used as the training objective due to its robustness to outliers, which are common in sensor degradation data. Optimization is performed using the AdamW optimizer, which applies decoupled weight decay to improve generalization [13]. Early stopping based on validation RMSE is applied to prevent overfitting.

4 Experimental Setup

This section outlines the dataset used, pre-processing pipeline, and configuration settings adopted to train and evaluate our RUL prediction models.

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed hybrid model architecture combining BiLSTM layers, a Transformer attention block, residual dilated CNNs, and CBAM for RUL prediction.

4.1 Dataset

We utilize the NASA C-MAPSS benchmark dataset [17], which simulate engine degradation across different operating conditions and fault modes. Each dataset contains multivariate time-series sensor measurements from turbofan engines recorded over successive operational cycles until failure.

- FD001: 100 train/test engines; 1 operating condition; 1 fault mode (HPC degradation).
- FD002: 260 train / 259 test engines; 6 operating conditions; 1 fault mode.
- FD003: 100 train / 100 test engines; 1 operating condition; 2 fault modes (HPC + fan degradation).
- FD004: 248 train / 249 test engines; 6 operating conditions; 2 fault modes.

Each engine unit begins operation in a healthy state and experiences gradual degradation. In the test set, degradation stops at an intermediate point, and the true Remaining Useful Life (RUL) is provided separately.

4.2 Data Preprocessing

To ensure consistency and suitability for model training, the following preprocessing pipeline is applied uniformly across all four data subsets. This process standardizes the input structure and quality, enabling reliable performance comparisons and model generalization across varying operating conditions and fault modes.

4.2.1 Remaining Useful Life Computation

For each training trajectory, RUL is computed as:

$$RUL_{i,t} = \max(\text{cycle}_i) - t$$

where t is the current time cycle of engine i . The RUL values are clipped at a maximum threshold (125) to stabilize training [14].

Figure 2: RUL distribution in the training set with a threshold cutoff line at 125 cycles.

4.2.2 Operating Condition Encoding

Operational settings are converted into categorical identifiers by rounding and concatenating the three setting values. This facilitates condition-specific scaling.

4.2.3 Sensor Selection and Normalization

Only a subset of informative sensors is retained, based on prior domain studies. These include: T24, T30, T50, P30, Nf, Nc, Ps30, phi, NRc, BPR, htBleed, W31, and W32. For each unique operating condition, a StandardScaler is fitted and applied independently to normalize the sensor signals [14, 29]. A detailed description of the selected sensors, including units and physical interpretations, is provided in the Appendix (Table 2)

4.2.4 Exponential Smoothing

To reduce sensor noise, exponential weighted moving average (EWMA) [6] smoothing with decay factor $\alpha = 0.3$ is applied. The first few smoothed cycles are discarded to mitigate filter delay.

4.2.5 Sequence Generation

The smoothed, normalized signals are segmented into fixed-length sequences (length = 30) using a sliding window. For training and validation, each sequence is associated with the RUL label of its final time step.

4.2.6 Train/Validation Split

GroupShuffleSplit is used to partition the training data into an 80/20 split based on engine unit IDs, ensuring no temporal leakage across sets.

4.2.7 Test Data Construction

For each test engine, only the final 30 time steps are retained, simulating the realistic prediction scenario. Padding is used if a trajectory is shorter than 30 cycles.

4.3 Implementation and Reproducibility

All experiments are conducted using Python 3.10 and TensorFlow on Google Colab. Reproducibility is ensured by setting random seeds and logging hyperparameters. Each dataset is evaluated independently using identical preprocessing and model configurations unless otherwise specified. The

Figure 3: Box plots of first 9 sensor readings across the training set, illustrating variability and outlier behavior among the sensors.

complete code and model weights for this work are available at: <https://github.com/rajatrayaraddi/rul-prediction-bilstm-cnn>.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Hyperparameter Optimization

Bayesian hyperparameter tuning [28] is performed using Keras Tuner to identify the optimal configuration for our proposed hybrid model. The best-performing setup included:

- BiLSTM layers with 96 and 48 units respectively
- Transformer block with 4 attention heads and feedforward dimension of 128
- Residual CNN blocks with 64 and 32 filters, both with a kernel size of 5
- Dense layer with 64 units
- Dropout rate of 0.3
- Learning rate of 0.000566 and weight decay of 1×10^{-5} using the AdamW optimizer

This configuration yielded a validation RMSE of 14.86 on FD002.

5.2 Comparison with Baselines

To evaluate the contribution of each architectural component, controlled experiments were conducted using standalone variants of commonly used deep learning models. Specifically, we implemented and trained individual models using:

- Stacked LSTM layers to model long-term temporal dependencies in sequential sensor data;
- Deep CNN architectures with multiple convolutional blocks to capture local patterns over time;

- Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs) with dilated causal convolutions to extend temporal receptive fields.

Each model was trained on the same preprocessed C-MAPSS dataset with identical data splits and training configurations (e.g., sequence length, RUL threshold, and batch size) to ensure fairness in comparison. Performance was evaluated using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) on all four FD subsets.

It was observed that the standalone CNN outperformed both LSTM and TCN models on average, likely due to its ability to extract robust local features without overfitting. In contrast, TCNs underperformed significantly, especially on datasets with higher variability in operating conditions (FD002 and FD004), suggesting limitations in generalizing across long sequences without additional contextual guidance. These results provided a foundation for our hybrid model design combining CNNs with BiLSTM and attention mechanisms.

Table 1 summarizes the test RMSE values across the four C-MAPSS subsets. Our hybrid BiLSTM-CNN-Transformer model outperforms the baseline Deep-LSTM [10] model and is competitive with the current state-of-the-art Recurrent Variational Encoding (RVE) approach [4].

Table 1: RMSE comparison across C-MAPSS subsets.

Model	FD001	FD002	FD003	FD004
SVR [34]	20.96	42.00	21.05	45.35
RVR [34]	23.80	31.30	22.37	34.34
CNN [34]	18.45	30.29	19.82	29.16
Semi-supervised [5]	12.56	22.73	12.10	22.66
DCNN [10]	12.61	22.36	12.64	23.31
MS-DCNN [10]	11.44	19.35	11.67	22.22
Deep-LSTM [34]	16.14	24.49	16.18	28.17
Recurrent Variational Encoding (SOTA) [4]	13.42	14.92	12.51	16.37
Our Model (BiLSTM-CNN-Transformer)	15.47	25.39	15.27	27.41
Our CNN	16.86	27.57	17.15	29.37
Standalone LSTM	21.96	31.43	20.17	30.64
TCN	29.29	41.85	30.92	46.23

While our model trails the SOTA in most cases (notably FD004), it provides gains over the Deep-LSTM and demonstrates promising generalization on subsets with complex operating conditions and fault modes.

5.3 Error Analysis

To evaluate the quality of predictions on FD002 in more detail, we present multiple visualizations:

- True vs. Predicted RUL (Figure 4): This plot illustrates how closely our model tracks the true degradation patterns. While short-term deviations occur, the model effectively captures the downward RUL trends across most units.
- Prediction Error Distribution (Figure 5): The histogram of prediction errors reveals a nearly symmetric distribution centered around zero, indicating low bias. Most errors fall within a ± 20 cycle range, suggesting stable performance.
- Error by Engine Units (Figure 6): RUL prediction errors across 50 randomly sampled engines. Errors vary slightly across units but remain within acceptable tolerance for deployment in real-world prognostic systems.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Conclusion

In this work, a hybrid deep learning architecture combining BiLSTM, dilated CNNs, and transformer-based attention mechanisms was presented for predicting the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of

Figure 4: True vs. Predicted Remaining Useful Life (RUL) for FD002 test data.

Figure 5: Distribution of prediction errors (True RUL – Predicted RUL) on FD002.

Figure 6: Prediction error across a random sample of 50 engine units from FD002.

complex machinery using the C-MAPSS dataset. Key innovations include the integration of positional encoding, CBAM attention for enhanced feature selection, and regularization techniques such as dropout, weight decay, and Huber loss. Our model demonstrates strong predictive performance across all four C-MAPSS subsets and outperforms traditional deep LSTM baselines. While our approach is outperformed by recent state-of-the-art methods like Recurrent Variational Encoding, it offers a simpler and modular architecture that remains competitive and interpretable.

6.2 Future Work

Future research could explore several directions:

- Uncertainty estimation through techniques such as Monte Carlo dropout or Bayesian neural networks to provide confidence intervals for RUL predictions.
- Online learning frameworks that incorporate feedback from real-time sensor data to continuously update and improve the model.
- Domain adaptation methods to better generalize across varying operating conditions and failure modes (e.g., FD002 and FD004).
- Integration into industrial systems, evaluating deployment feasibility, real-time inference efficiency, and operator interpretability.
- Explainability and diagnostics, leveraging attention maps or saliency techniques to provide insights into sensor influence and failure precursors.

These extensions would enhance the robustness, applicability, and trustworthiness of RUL prediction systems in real-world predictive maintenance pipelines.

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A Appendix

Table 2: List of selected sensors with descriptions and units

Symbol	Description	Units
T24	Total temperature at LPC outlet	°R
T30	Total temperature at HPC outlet	°R
T50	Total temperature at LPT outlet	°R
P30	Total pressure at HPC outlet	psia
Nf	Physical fan speed	rpm
Nc	Physical core speed	rpm
Ps30	Static pressure at HPC outlet	psia
phi	Ratio of fuel flow to Ps30	pps/psi
NRc	Corrected core speed	rpm
BPR	Bypass Ratio	–
htBleed	Bleed Enthalpy	–
W31	HPT coolant bleed	lbm/s
W32	LPT coolant bleed	lbm/s